

GraspOS Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

Funder

European Commission||
EC

Grant

GraspOS: next Generation
Research Assessment to
Promote Open Science/
No 101095129

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Organizations

Università degli Studi di BOLOGNA, OPENAIRE AMKE,
LEIDEN UNIVERSITY, TSV, CSC - IT Center for Science
(Finland), University of Eastern Finland, ATHENA
Research Center, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche -
Istituto di Informatica e Telematica

Datasets

Title: BIP! DB

Template: Horizon Europe

BIP! DB is an open dataset that contains a variety of impact measures calculated for a large collection of scientific publications from various disciplines.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

This dataset is based on the integration of three major datasets, which provide citation data: OpenCitation's COCI dataset, Microsoft Academic Graph, and Crossref.

Based on these data, we perform citation network analysis to produce five useful impact measures, which capture distinctly different aspects of scientific impact.

Note that this dataset is already available in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4386934>); in the context of the GraspOS project, we plan to extend it, ensuring regular updates.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

BIP! DB is an open dataset that contains a variety of impact measures calculated for a large collection scientific publications from various disciplines.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

More than 25GB when compressed

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To combine with other data

The impact measures that BIP! DB offers, can be invaluable, since they can effectively quantify the scientific impact of research works.

These impact measures are calculated in the DOI and OpenAIRE id level, thus they can be easily integrated, and combined with other datasets.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

BIP! DB gathers citation data and metadata from three data sources: OpenCitations' COCI dataset, Microsoft's Academic Graph (MAG), and Crossref.

The dataset production workflow collects, cleans, and integrates data from these sources to produce a citation graph based on the distinct DOI-to-DOI relationships found.

Since the publication year is required for some of the measures to be calculated, publications lacking this information were excluded from the final network.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

Identifying the most valuable publications for any given research topic has become extremely tedious and time consuming.

Therefore, quantifying the impact of scientific works could facilitate the related tasks, which make up the daily routine of researchers and other professionals of the broader scientific and academic community.

Note that all impact indicators can be aggregated in the level of the researcher, organisation (RPO or RFO) or country to facilitate research monitoring.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

BIP! DB: A Dataset of Impact Measures for Scientific Publications

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

All files published are freely available in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4386934>) under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

The described output uses BIP! Ranker (<https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker>) to calculate impact indicators. Additionally, BIP! DB is used as the underlying data of the BIP! Services (<https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/>).

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

For each calculation level (DOI / OpenAIRE-id) we provide five (5) compressed CSV files (one for each measure/score provided) where each line follows the format "identifier <tab> score <tab> class". The parameter setting of each measure is encoded in the corresponding filename.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Through Zenodo API and portal.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Through Zenodo API.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, it assigns depositions with a DOI.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

BIP! DB: A Dataset of Impact Measures for Scientific Publications

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes, the dump will be uploaded in Zenodo, so it will be accessible after the end of the project.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

The fairness of additional resources produced in the context of this project have been already taken into account in the funding.

In addition, Open Science tools (e.g., Zenodo) are utilized whenever possible, so no additional cost will incur.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Thanasis Vergoulis (orcid:0000-0003-0555-4128)
- b. Serafeim Chatzopoulos (orcid:0000-0003-1714-5225)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Since it is uploaded on Zenodo, it is responsible for the long term preservation of the dataset.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Note that we collect, process on-the-fly, and display in our UI the user's public information in their ORCID account to support the functionality of BIP! Scholar. However, we do not plan to process or share this information.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [OpenAIRE Usage Counts](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

UsageCounts service collects usage data from Open Science data sources, like repositories, journals, etc, aggregates them and delivers standardized activity reports about research usage.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Usage events collected by Open Science Datasources. A usage event could be:

- A metadata view of the digital object
- A full text download

Usage events are collected using either:

- a Push approach that allows server side tracking by employing dedicated software to track the usage events.
- a Pull approach which supports the gathering of consolidated already available usage statistics reports from aggregators.

1.1.5 What is its format?

7-bit ANSI Text

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

A few MB (megabytes)

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Primary data

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/resources#apis>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

API endpoints

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

API endpoints

- <https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/resources#apis>

- https://beta.services.openaire.eu/usagestats_r5/

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Up to 5 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/COUNTER/counter-sushi_5_0_api/5.0.3

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

GNU Affero General Public License v3

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Dimitrios Pierrakos (orcid:0000-0001-6788-4128)

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Pilots' analysis data

Template: Horizon Europe

Descriptive data on the pilot settings in terms of their research evaluation aims, context and resources is collected of each of the nine pilots. The data consist of nine individual pilot analyses describing 1) their state of affairs in terms of open science and research assessment practices, tools, services and datasets used, and identified gaps, 2) their evaluation context, and 3) their ambitions in terms of developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science. The analyses are conducted following a template.

The data is used to

- a) compile a summative report on pilot setup, current practices and initial requirements as a project deliverable,
- b) facilitate shaping of the pilot evaluation event focused on open science practices to support WP2, and
- c) provide information on the initial requirements and the current best practices for indicators, data, tools and services to support WP3 and WP4.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Pilots' self-assessment reports on their research evaluation aims, context and resources.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Word Document

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

< 3MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

The obtained data will be utilised in the development of Open Science Assessment Framework, Openness Profile, and indicators, data, tools and services.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data is collected from each of the pilots using a word template designed as part of the project.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Other

others include: research policy makers, those who conduct assessment of research and researchers, and research funders.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

General Finnish Ontology YSO is a trilingual (Finnish, Swedish, English) ontology consisting mainly of general concepts. YSO has been founded on

the basis of concepts in Finnish cultural sphere. As an indexing tool it is best applicable when indexed material is interdisciplinary and its themes vary to a great extent. YSO has also been linked to Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH).

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

monitoring, Research, Open Science

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Pilots' analysis data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The data on pilots' research evaluation aims, context and resources is collected solely for the purpose of supporting WP2, WP3 and WP4 in their development work. The analyses are made available only within the project. A summative report based on the analyses will be published and made openly accessible.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

General Finnish Ontology YSO

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

The data collected will not be openly available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

Storage

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

The fairness of additional resources produced in the context of this project have been already taken into account in the funding.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

As the pilots have not submitted their analyses yet it is not possible to know at this point if there are any ethical issues impacting the sharing of the dataset, or if it contains personal data.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Unknown

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Unkown

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Cherry Repository](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

The Repository aims to operate according to the FAIR principles. All preservation actions are focused on ensuring that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

- Archiving of the participating institutions' heritage (publications, research data, etc.);

- Ensuring long-term preservation of publications and other types of research outputs;

- It serves as a dissemination tool and a data provider for multiple aggregators;

- It is a data source for further research;

- It ensures compliance with national, institutional and funder Open Access policies and FAIR principles.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Acrobat PDF/A - Portable Document Format
- OpenDocument Text
- netCDF-3 64-bit
- OpenDocument Spreadsheet
- CSV Schema
- Structured Query Language Data
- SIARD (Software-Independent Archiving of Relational Databases)
- SPSS Portable Data Format
- Stata Data (DTA) Format
- Tagged Image File Format
- Portable Network Graphics
- JPEG File Interchange Format
- JP2 (JPEG 2000 part 1)
- Scalable Vector Graphics
- Material Exchange Format
- Matroska
- FLAC (Free Lossless Audio Codec)
- Ogg Opus Codec Compressed Multimedia File
- SDSC Image Tool Wavefront Raster Image
- Polygon File Format
- X3D

- RDF/XML
- Turtle
- JSON-LD

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Not specified.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- The public

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

List of project identifiers: <https://nardus.mpn.gov.rs/Files/projectData.xml>.

Each project has its own code to be entered.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Supplementary material for: Ferjančić, Z., Kukuruzar, A., & Bihelović, F.. (2022). Total Synthesis of (+)-Alstonlarsine A. in *Angewandte Chemie International Edition Wiley*, 61(39), e202210297. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202210297>

dc.creator	Ferjančić, Zorana	
dc.creator	Kukuruzar, Andrej	
dc.creator	Bihelović, Filip	
dc.date.accessioned	2023-03-21T16:50:43Z	
dc.date.available	2023-03-21T16:50:43Z	
dc.date.issued	2022	
dc.identifier.idn	1433-7851	
dc.identifier.url	http://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5844	
dc.description.abstract	An enantioselective total synthesis of (+)-alstonlarsine A (1), a monoterpene indole alkaloid possessing a unique pentacyclic skeleton as well as a rare biological activity, is achieved. The key step is an efficient domino sequence, comprising enamine formation followed by an inverse-electron-demand intramolecular dearomative Diels-Alder cycloaddition for the construction of 9-azatricyclo[4.3.1.0 ^{3,8}]decane core. The key intermediate for this domino sequence was synthesized by a newly developed methodology, relying on indole C(2)-H bond functionalization, combined with intramolecular Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction. This tactical combination offers a new general entry into other (privileged) tricyclic frameworks possessing indole ring fused to 6-, 7- or 8-membered rings.	sr
dc.language.iso	en	sr
dc.publisher	Wiley	sr
dc.relation	info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/ScienceFundRS/Idjeje/7750119/RS/	sr
dc.relation.isreferencedby	https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5842	
dc.relation.isreferencedby	https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202210297	
dc.rights	openAccess	sr
dc.rights.url	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/	
dc.source	Angewandte Chemie International Edition	sr
dc.subject	Alkaloids	sr
dc.subject	Carbenoids	sr
dc.subject	Diels Alder Cycloaddition	sr
dc.subject	Domino Reactions	sr
dc.subject	Total Synthesis	sr
dc.title	Supplementary material for: Ferjančić, Z., Kukuruzar, A., & Bihelović, F.. (2022). Total Synthesis of (+)-Alstonlarsine A. in <i>Angewandte Chemie International Edition Wiley</i> , 61(39), e202210297. https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202210297	sr
dc.type	dataset	sr
dc.rightslicense	BY-SA	sr
dc.citation.volume	61	
dc.citation.issue	39	
dc.citation.epage	e202210297	
dc.description.other	Supplementary material for: [https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202210297]	
dc.description.other	Related to published version: [https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5842]	
dc.description.other	Related to accepted version: [https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5843]	
dc.type.version	publishedVersion	sr
dc.identifier.rcub	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_cherry_5844	

Image 1

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Legal

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository
- Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Cherry Repository

<https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use

- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The reason is sensitive data. Cherry repository currently does not contain sensitive data. However, a procedure for handling potentially sensitive data is defined and the software platform and repository managers can support sophisticated access control (<https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC5x/Functional+Overview#FunctionalOverview-Authorization>) and prevent sensitive data from becoming exposed or compromised.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The primary objective of the Repository is to provide infrastructure for archiving, long-term preservation, wide dissemination and Open Access, when possible, to research data from the European and national projects implemented by the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry. Research data will be accessed during and after the project GraspOS ends.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

Subject controlled vocabularies are currently not implemented in the Repository but users are encouraged to define keywords relying on controlled vocabularies relevant for their discipline.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Dublin Core

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The metadata are exposed via the Open Archives Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

Not specified.

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Ana Djordjevic (orcid:0000-0002-8654-7693)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The primary objective of the Repository is to provide infrastructure for archiving, long-term preservation, wide dissemination and Open Access, when possible, to publications and other research outputs resulting from the GraspOS project and other activities implemented by the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry. As the initial steps towards archiving research data are being made, the Repository should also ensure that these data are available in the long term for reuse, replication and verification purposes.

The national Open Science policy (<https://open.ac.rs/images/doc/Open-Science-Policy-Serbia.pdf>, 2018) assumes an indefinitely long retention period for publications. According to the Code of Conduct in Research (2018), the recommended retention period for research data is at least 5 years (preferably 10 years). In the context of the Repository, the long term is certainly longer than 10 years.

The Preservation policy relies on the main functional concepts of the Open Archival Information System (<http://www.oais.info/>) reference model for digital preservation environments and the FAIR principles. Preservation decisions are made taking into consideration the Repository's mission, Content policy, legal constraints and available human, technical and financial resources.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Privacy policies
- National laws

Repository currently focuses on the materials that are or can eventually be made publicly available. The institutions using the Repository are still in the process of developing their data policies, and the Designated Community is not expected to deposit sensitive data until the policies are fully defined (3-5 years). However, a procedure for handling potentially sensitive data is in place; the software platform fully supports sophisticated access control (by defining users or user groups who can access data at the bitstream level: <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC5x/Functional+Overview#FunctionalOverview-Authorization>), and the repository manager, who is employed by the participating institution, is trained and authorized to prevent sensitive data from becoming exposed or compromised.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [OpenCitations data](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

This dataset contains appropriate dumps of all the OpenCitations collections, particularly the OpenCitations Index and OpenCitations Meta. These two collections contain citation data and bibliographic metadata gathered from different sources (Crossref, DataCite, the National Institute of Health Open Citation Collection, and the OpenAIRE Graph) and are made available by OpenCitations. This independent, community-led, and not-for-profit Open Science infrastructure organisation publishes such data as open material (licensed using a CC0 waiver) using Linked Data technologies.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

All data in any OpenCitations collection are derived from other existing sources (as described in 1.1.8). Other sources can be added in the future.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Comma Separated Values
- JSON Data Interchange Format
- JSON-LD
- Turtle

All the data are provided in different formats. In particular, we use CSV and JSON-LD (RDF) for basic bibliographic metadata. Instead, for citation data, we use CSV, Scholix (JSON), and N-quads/N-triples (RDF)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To combine with other data

OpenCitations aims to harvest and openly publish accurate and comprehensive metadata describing the world's academic publications and the scholarly citations that link them and to preserve ongoing access to this information by secure archiving. We provide this information, both in human-readable form and in interoperable machine-readable Linked Open Data formats, under open licenses at zero cost and without restriction for third-party analysis and re-use.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

We use, as sources, several trusted providers of bibliographic metadata and citation data, and currently includes:

* Crossref

* DataCite

* the National Institute of Health Open Citation Collection

* the OpenAIRE Graph

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry

The OpenCitations stakeholder community includes universities and research institutions, academic and national libraries, scholarly publishers, research and data infrastructures, national governments and international organisations, research funders and philanthropic organisations, companies working in the scholarly ecosystem, software and service developers, academic policy-makers, independent scholars and ordinary citizens.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

OpenCitations, an infrastructure organization for open scholarship

Quantitative Science Studies

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/opencitations/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Crossref

In addition to the specified persistent identifiers scheme, we currently handle PubMed Id, PubMed Central Id, and arXiv Id.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

We provide the basic metadata of the dumps of OpenCitations collection following the mask adopted in the repository we use to deposit them - i.e. Figshare - that are then made available on Crossref.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

They are available and stored in Figshare and made available through Crossref.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

OpenCitations

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

They can be harvested by using REST APIs and via SPARQL endpoints.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

figshare

<https://figshare.org>

Figshare is a repository where users can make all of their research outputs available in a citable, shareable and discoverable manner.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, figshare assigns DOIs to all the datasets uploaded there.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

OpenCitations data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

All data in the OpenCitations collection are licensed using a CC0 waiver.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

OpenCitations

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

REST APIs and SPARQL endpoints

<http://opencitations.net/querying>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

OpenCitations is an independent infrastructure organisation which several stakeholders around the world support. Any provided data will be accessible during the project and will continue to be after it ends.

OpenCitations do not collect any personal information of the user using the data.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The data dumps will be available in the long term in Figshare. All other services for accessing them programmatically are tied to the sustainability of OpenCitations, which aims to be supported in the next decade at least.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

The OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM, <https://opencitations.net/model>) describes all the data in OpenCitations collections. It is based on SPAR Ontologies (<http://www.sparontologies.net>) and PROV-O (<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>).

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The adoption of specific Semantic Web formats and ontologies to foster technical and semantic data interoperability, coupled with Linked Open Data technologies.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset per se is not connected to other resources via qualified links. However, it indeed describes links between publication entities and other contextual information, and such links are all qualified ("Entity A cites Entity B", "Entity A has been authored by Agent C", etc.). Please note that the dataset itself can be described in its data as one of the entities that have been cited by

someone else.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The OpenCitations Data Model has an entire module dedicated to keep track of provenance information and data change tracking (i.e. how data are modified in time).

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

130000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

- Re-use
- Other

Processing data (gathering, cleaning, transforming, publishing, etc.), Personnel, Software development and maintenance, Hardware maintenance, furnishings (e.g. electricity, server rooms)

Direct cost

Making available and updated FAIR bibliographic and citation data pass through a complex workflow involving people, software and hardware is very difficult to estimate. The cost specified concerns only the people/activity strictly related to the production and publication of the data, excluding other expenses for keeping the infrastructure (at organisational level and technical level) running.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Infrastructure Grant
- Collaboration with other Projects

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Silvio Peroni (orcid:0000-0003-0530-4305)

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Interview transcriptions

Template: Horizon Europe

A dataset containing the transcriptions of the interviews that will be conducted at the University of Eastern Finland in 2024.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The dataset will be generated within the research.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The dataset is primary data that will be collected and analysed for the first time within the research.

1.1.5 What is its format?

AbiWord Document

The dataset consists of interview transcriptions that will be produced and stored as word documents.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

500 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

The dataset consisting of interview transcriptions is collected in order to obtain information that does not yet exist.

The interviews explore the views of the leaders and experts of the University of Eastern Finland on the uses of less-used publication indicators (so called new indicators) in the knowledge management and in the research assessment of the university.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset is generated via interviews conducted at the University of Eastern Finland.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers

The dataset will be used within the research.

The dataset of interview transcriptions is used as the background data of a case study exploring the benefits and uses of less-used publication indicators at one university. Since the dataset collected in the case study covers only one individual university, the amount of data is quite limited (5-10 interview transcripts). The possibilities of reusing a small case study dataset are limited.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Descriptive metadata containing e.g. title, author/creator, date and administrative data containing e.g. licence, ownership will be provided for the dataset.

The metadata is used in the management of the research and in administrative purposes within the research.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

Descriptive metadata containing e.g. title, author/creator, date, and administrative metadata containing e.g. license, ownership will be provided for the dataset.

The metadata is used in the management of the research and in administrative purposes within the research.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

YSO - General Finnish Ontology is a trilingual (Finnish, Swedish, English) ontology consisting mainly of general concepts. YSO has been founded on the basis of concepts in Finnish cultural sphere. As an indexing tool it is best applicable when indexed material is interdisciplinary and its themes vary to a great extent.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Finnish and/or English keyword and tags are provided in the metadata.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

The dataset of interview transcriptions is used as the background data of a case study exploring the benefits and uses of less-used publication indicators at one university. Since the dataset collected in the case study covers only one individual university, the amount of data is quite limited (5-10 interview transcripts). The possibilities of reusing a small case study dataset are limited.

The case study is carried out in and by an individual university. The university and the university leaders and experts interviewed can be identified by reasoning, even if the dataset is anonymised.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The dataset of interview transcriptions is used as the background data of a case study exploring the benefits and uses of less-used publication indicators at one university. Since the dataset collected in the case study covers only one individual university, the amount of data is quite limited (5-10 interview transcripts). The possibilities of reusing a small case study dataset are limited.

The case study is carried out in and by an individual university. The university and the university leaders and experts interviewed can be identified by reasoning, even if the dataset is anonymised.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During and after the project ends, the dataset is saved on personal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space of the University of Eastern Finland. The dataset can be accessed by the researchers involved: Heikki Laitinen and Katri Rintamäki.

The dataset is saved on personal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space of the university involved. The University is responsible for the security of its information systems according to its information processing instructions.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The dataset will not be preserved or made accessible in the long term, but for 5 years after the end of the research in 2025, until the end of the year 2030. The dataset will be disposed in the beginning of the 2031.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Descriptive metadata containing e.g. title, author/creator, and date, and administrative metadata containing e.g. license and ownership will be provided for the dataset.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

The dataset can be accessed by the researchers involved.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

The metadata will remain available after the dataset is no longer available.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

YSO - General Finnish ontology <https://finto.fi/ys0/en/>

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes

YSO - General Finnish Ontology is linked to Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH).

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

The dataset of interview transcriptions is used as the background data of a case study. Since the dataset collected in the case study covers only one individual university, the amount of data is quite limited (5-10 interview transcripts). The possibilities of reusing a small case study dataset are limited.

The case study is carried out in and by an individual university. The university and the university leaders and experts interviewed can be identified by reasoning, even if the dataset is anonymised.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

The dataset consists of interview transcriptions. The documentation of data provenance is not relevant.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

The dataset consists of interview transcriptions of 5-10 interviews. There is no need for more advanced quality assurance procedures for the small dataset.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

Direct cost

There is no direct cost on storing the dataset on the university server by employees of the university.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

The dataset will be saved on personal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space of the university involved. There is no direct cost on storing the dataset on the university storage / disk space.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Katri Rintamäki (orcid:0000-0001-9729-4647)

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Heikki Laitinen

Researchers' data management and stewardship activities: data collection, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving and sharing.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

The dataset will be saved on personal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space of the university involved.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

The dataset will be saved on personal LocalDrive storage or secured researcher disk space of the university involved. Data recovery, secure storage, and transfer of sensitive data procedures are included.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The dataset will not be preserved in the long term, but for 5 years after the end of the research in 2025, until the end of the year 2030. The dataset will be disposed in the beginning of the 2031.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

The dataset consists of interviews exploring the views of the leaders and experts of one university on the use of less widely used publication indicators (so called new indicators) in knowledge management and in the evaluation of research activities at the university.

The case study is carried out in and by an individual university. The university and the university leaders and experts interviewed can be identified by reasoning, even if the dataset is anonymised.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [OpenAIRE Graph](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

The OpenAIRE Graph is a service that populates and provides access to a Scholarly Communication Graph (SKG) that includes metadata and links between scientific products (e.g. literature, datasets, software, "other research products"), organizations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and (provenance) data sources.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The OpenAIRE Graph includes scholarly data, i.e., metadata and links between research products (e.g. literature, datasets, software), organizations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and data sources.

1.1.5 What is its format?

JSON Data Interchange Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

More than 100GB of storage when compressed.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To develop a product

We share information aggregated from different data sources, deduplicate, enrich them, and make them available in different formats, portals and APIs.

We provide services upon the data, that can be used to develop a product.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Metadata records are collected from different data sources, including Open Access institutional repositories, data archives, journals etc.

They are further enriched with records from Crossref, Unpaywall, DataCite, ORCID, ROR, and information about projects provided by national and international funders.

Dedicated inference algorithms applied to metadata and full-texts of Open Access publications enrich the content with links between research results and projects, author affiliations, subject classification, links to entries from domain-specific databases.

Duplicated organizations, data sources and results are identified and merged together in a unified form.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

Researchers can explore research outputs on specific topics, since the OpenAIRE Graph collects data from the most common and large data sources.

Research communities can have dedicated gateways, gathering their research outputs.

Decision makers to evaluate the outcomes of a funding stream.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

The dataset will be uploaded on Zenodo, that assigns a DOI. All contributing authors will provide their ORCID and eventually it would be linked with the related project. Furthermore, the metadata will have a description, and will be linked to the relevant resources describing the schema of the data contained in the dataset.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Through Zenodo API and portal.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Through Zenodo APIs.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is a catch-all repository hosted at CERN.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, it provides a DOI.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

The OpenAIRE Graph dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will be hosted at Zenodo, as such, it will be freely available to download.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

It provides reference to the schema of the data within the dataset.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes, the dump will be uploaded in Zenodo, so it will be accessible after the end of the project.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Yes, every record included in the dataset has dedicated information for its provenance.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

This dataset will be based on the OpenAIRE graph, an open resource that is already FAIR.

Furthermore, the fairness of additional resources produced in the context of this project have been already taken into account in the funding.

Last but not least, Open Science tools (e.g., Zenodo) are utilized whenever possible, so no additional cost will incur.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Claudio Atzori (orcid:0000-0001-9613-6639)
- b. Miriam Baglioni (orcid:0000-0002-2273-9004)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

It is preserved via uploaded in Zenodo.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Scholexplorer

Template: Horizon Europe

Scholexplorer is a service that populates and provides access to a graph of links between dataset and literature objects and dataset and dataset objects. Links (and objects) are provided by data sources managed by publishers, data centers, or other organisations providing services to store and manage links between data sets and publications, such as CrossRef, DataCite, and OpenAIRE. Scholexplorer aggregates link metadata harvested from the data sources and builds and harmonised and de-duplicated graph of scholarly objects. The graph is accessible via API or Dump on Zenodo. Such data dump is the subject of this DMP.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The Scholexplorer datasets includes scholarly links in [scholix metadata format](#) between research products (e.g. literature, datasets, software).

1.1.5 What is its format?

JSON Data Interchange Format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

200GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Open Science Scholarly Communication Workflows - The OpenAIRE infrastructure and Scholexplorer Service

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

research data, Research Software, Publications

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer Service: Scholix JSON Dump

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

ScholarXplorer is an open resource that is already FAIR. Open Science tools (e.g., Zenodo) are utilized whenever possible, so no additional cost will incur.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

It is preserved via uploading in Zenodo.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: OPERAS Metrics

Template: Horizon Europe

The service collects usage and alternative metrics for OA monographs and books: downloads, web visits, tweets, wikipedia mentions, etc. It is based on a shared data model.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Usage metrics metadata of open access books via service providers.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

Structured Query Language Data

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

13.8 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Google Analytics

Matomo

Access Logs

Google Books

Open Edition

OAPEN

JSTOR

World Reader

Unglue.it

OpenAIRE

IRUS-UK

Wikiversity

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public
- Industry
- Other

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/hirmeos>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

Usage metrics are generated by using PIDs, but not producing them itself.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0.0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant
- Collaboration with other Projects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Community of Practice Contact Information

Template: Horizon Europe

A dataset containing contact information (only email; name and affiliation are voluntary) for the purpose of inviting to online events concerning the Community of Practice (T6.2.) as described in GraspOS deliverable D6.2.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.5 What is its format?

Microsoft Excel 4.0 Workbook (xls)

tbd

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

90kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

Other

To contact potentially interested participants to the CoP.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Other

None. Only us.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

GraspOS CoP Contact Information

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Not an output

Not an output

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Will be deleted by the end of GraspOS.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

x

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

GraspOS Project Website handler / organisation

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

tbd by GraspOS website operator

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Will not preserve in the long term; will be deleted after GraspOS ends.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Other

Only emails will be collected for contacting. Data will be deleted after they fulfilled their purpose. GDPR related concerns are described on the website where emails are submitted.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: OSAF - Landscape Survey on Reforming Research Assessment

Template: Horizon Europe

A dataset containing responses to the questionnaire for the purpose to gain overview of the state-of-the-art research assessment practices at the research performing, funding and evaluating organisations who already are, or could become, signatories of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Survey results

1.1.5 What is its format?

CSV

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

About 200 KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To develop a product

The obtained data will be utilized in the development of Open Science Assessment Framework

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Survey results are collected using the LimeSurvey web app, which is a free and open source on-line statistical survey web app written in PHP based on a MySQL, SQLite, PostgreSQL or MSSQL database, distributed under the GNU General Public License.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Other

Others include: research policy makers, those who conduct assessment of research and researchers.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

The dataset will be uploaded on Zenodo, that assigns a DOI. All contributing authors will provide their ORCID and eventually it would be linked with the related project. Furthermore, the metadata will have a description, and will be linked to the relevant resources describing the schema of the data contained in the dataset.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

General Finnish Ontology YSO is a trilingual (Finnish, Swedish, English) ontology consisting mainly of general concepts. YSO has been founded on the basis of concepts in Finnish cultural sphere. As an indexing tool it is best applicable when indexed material is interdisciplinary and its themes vary to a great extent. YSO has also been linked to Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH).

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

survey data, Research, Open Science

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is a catch-all repository hosted in CERN

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, it provides a DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Landscape Survey on Reforming Research Assessment

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

General Finnish Ontology YSO

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes, the survey results will be uploaded to Zenodo, so it will be accessible after the end of the project

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage

- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

The fairness of additional resources produced in the context of this project have been already taken into account in the funding.

Open Science tools (e.g. Zenodo) are utilized whenever possible, so no additional costs will incur.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Janne Pölönen (orcid:0000-0003-1649-0879)

Plan and Design

Collect and Capture

Collaborate and Analyse

Manage, Store and Preserve

Share and Publish

b. Anna-Kaisa Hyrkkänen (orcid:0009-0008-9173-286X)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Plan and Design
Collect and Capture
Collaborate and Analyse
Manage, Store and Preserve
Share and Publish

c. Marita Kari (orcid:0000-0003-2929-4279)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Plan and Design
Collect and Capture
Collaborate and Analyse

d. Dragan Ivanović (orcid:0000-0002-9942-5521)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Plan and Design
Collect and Capture
Collaborate and Analyse

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

It is preserved via upload in Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [OSAF - Landscape questionnaire for pilots](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

A dataset containing responses to the questionnaire that was addressed to pilot institutions to survey the current research assessment practices and to monitor to what extent the current situation of the pilot institutions are in relation to the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Survey results

1.1.5 What is its format?

CSV

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

About 200kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To develop a product

The obtained data will be utilized in the development of Open Science Assessment Framework.

The obtained data is used to measure pilot's current status of the research assessment practices and systems and it will be also used to position the pilot's level of maturity towards a research assessment reform.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Survey results are collected using the LimeSurvey web app, which is a free and open source on-line statistical survey web app written in PHP based on a MySQL, SQLite, PostgreSQL or MSSQL database, distributed under the GNU General Public License.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Other

The data is mainly useful for GraspOS project on the development work of Open Science Assessment Framework

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

The dataset will be uploaded on Zenodo, that assigns a DOI. All contributing authors will provide their ORCID and eventually it would be linked with the related project. Furthermore, the metadata will have a description, and will be linked to the relevant resources describing the schema of the data contained in the dataset.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

General Finnish Ontology YSO is a trilingual (Finnish, Swedish, English) ontology consisting mainly of general concepts. YSO has been founded on the basis of concepts in Finnish cultural sphere. As an indexing tool it is best applicable when indexed material is interdisciplinary and its themes vary to a great extent. YSO has also been linked to Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH).

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

survey data, Research, Open Science

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is a catch-all repository hosted in CERN

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Follows repository standards

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, it provides a DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Landscape questionnaire for pilots

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

General Finnish Ontology YSO

<https://finto.fi/yso/en/>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes, the survey data will be uploaded to Zenodo, so it will be accessible after the end of the project

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

N/A

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

The fairness of additional resources produced in the context of this project have been already taken into account in the funding.

Open Science tools (e.g. Zenodo) are utilized whenever possible, so no additional costs will incur.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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Share and Publish

c. Marita Kari (orcid:0000-0003-2929-4279)

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Collect and Capture
Collaborate and Analyse

d. Dragan Ivanović (orcid:0000-0002-9942-5521)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Plan and Design
Collect and Capture
Collaborate and Analyse

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

It is preserved via upload in Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: OPERAS GoTriple data

Template: Horizon Europe

The GoTriple service collects metadata on publications, datasets, authors and projects in the SSH field, providing automated enrichments for descriptive topics. GoTriple data is collected through OAI-PMH and database dumps. The GoTriple dataset is made available online through the platform's website, and through APIs and an OAI-PMH repository.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

GoTriple data is metadata generated by other repositories, and refined and enriched by the service. The metadata is freely accessible and harvested from aggregators (e.g. OpenAIRE, BASE, Isidore) or single repositories (e.g. OpenEdition, EKT publishing).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

The GoTriple dataset contains metadata about research outputs exclusively in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) field, including: publications, grey literature, training materials, datasets. The metadata of datasets comes currently mostly from the social sciences and the linguistics fields and corresponds to various types: tabular files, video recordings, audio recordings, etc.

The GoTriple dataset also contains metadata about projects in the SSH

1.1.5 What is its format?

8-bit ANSI Text

The GoTriple dataset consists only of strings of characters stored as binary files.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

80Gb for the Elasticsearch data files for the front-end indexes and around 95Gb for the cache.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To share information

GoTriple reuses existing metadata in order to provide an exhaustive access point to the entire production of the SSH fields in the European research area.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Here is the full list of data providers (in the case of multidisciplinary repositories, only SSH contents metadata is harvested):

DOAB: directory of open access books in all disciplines

DOAJ: directory of open access journals in all disciplines

Isidore: directory of scientific resources in the SSH

OpenAIRE: directory of scientific resources in all disciplines

Biblioteka Nauki: platform of open access publications in all disciplines

EKT publishing: platform of open access publications in all disciplines

EKT National Archive of PhD Theses

EKT Searchculture.gr

OAPEN: platform of open access publications in all disciplines

ZRC SAZU: platform of open access publications in all disciplines

CESSDA: platform of research data in the social sciences

BASE: directory of scientific resources in all disciplines

Europeana: platform of scientific resources about cultural heritage

CLARIN centers: platforms of research data in linguistics

Econstor: directory of open access publications in economics

OpenEdition: platform of open access publications in the SSH

Pombalina: platform of open access publications in the SSH

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

- Education
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

PIDs stored and exposed in the GoTriple datasets are retrieved not created by the service.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

TRIPLE DATA MODEL

Data model	Schema.org	Description
		Document id in TRIPLE
Abstract	schema:abstract	Abstract or description of the document
Author	schema:author	Authors of the document and link to profile(s). List of author ids.
Contributor	schema:contributor	List of contributors
Document type	schema:additionalType	Type of the document (given by aggregators)
Funding reference	schema:funder	List of project ids
Identifier	schema:identifier	List of identifiers
Keywords	schema:keywords	List of producer's keywords
Language	schema:inLanguage	Language of the content
License	schema:license	A license or a type of license
Primary producer	schema:producer	Primary producer of the doc (eg: HALSHS)
Publication date	schema:datePublished	Date of publication or creation
Publisher	schema:publisher	List of publishers
Sources information	schema:mentions	Source (free text) from: dc:source, dcterms:source (e.g. journal issue)
Sources URL	schema:isBasedOnURL	Source (HTTP) from: dc:source, dcterms:source (e.g. URL from a publishing platform)
Spatial location of dataset	schema:spatialCoverage	Content's spatial location of collection (list)
Subject (MORESS categories)	sioc:topic	List of MORESS Categories (disciplines)
Temporal period of dataset	schema:temporalCoverage	Content's temporal period of collection (list)
Title	schema:headline	Title of document
TRIPLE thesaurus	schema:knowsAbout	TRIPLE thesaurus entries
URL of full document	schema:url	URL of full text
URL of the landing page	schema:mainEntityOfPage	URL of landing page to the document.
Format	schema:encodingFormat	File format (multiple values)
Aggregator	schema:provider	Aggregator of the doc (eg: Isidore)
Access Rights	schema:conditionsOfAccess	Information on access status

Image 2

GoTriple uses the TRIPLE data model, which is aligned with Dublin Core and OpenAIRE guidelines, and expressed in the schema.org ontology.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/resource_types/

Controlled vocabulary for resource types

b. <https://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html>

Controlled vocabulary of topics for generic bibliographic description.

c. <http://semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH>

SSH concepts extracted from LCSH thesaurus and translated in 12 languages.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Keywords are added by the original providers.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GoTriple APIs

GoTriple APIs are available at: <https://api.gotriple.eu/>, where the APIs are described.

The endpoint for OAI-PMH repository is available at:
<https://api.gotriple.eu/oai2>

Full documentation available at: De Santis, Luca. (2022). TRIPLE Deliverable: D6.6 API's Development -RP3 (Draft). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371832>.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

GoTriple dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

GoTriple platform: <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

GoTriple APIs: <https://api.gotriple.eu/>

GoTriple OAI-PMH endpoint: <https://api.gotriple.eu/oai2>

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

GoTriple Discovery platform

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GoTriple APIs

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

REST APIs, see above.

<https://api.gotriple.eu/>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will be maintained by the supporting organization of the platform, the European OPERAS RI.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata about access rights and licensing are provided whenever made available by the original provider.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

GoTriple vocabulary for SSH: <http://semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH>

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

See above: <http://semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH>.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Dublin Core

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

The harvested metadata may contain references to other outputs, but the service doesn't support such links.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

GoTriple accepts a series of standardized open licenses (e.g. MIT, CC, etc.).

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

CCO Metadata will be maintained together with the platform managing it.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Metadata contains information on harvesting provenance.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use
- Security

Costs for FAIRification were included in the service development.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Arnaud Gingold

OPERAS FAIR data officer

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall

- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Metadata collected is available under CC0 license.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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